

INFLUENCE OF TEST RIG CONFIGURATION AND EVALUATION ALGORITHMS ON OPTICAL RADIAL-FLOW PERMEABILITY MEASUREMENT: A BENCHMARK EXERCISE

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ABSTRACT

While measuring the in-plane permeability of textile preforms via linear-flow experiments has recently been studied in an international benchmark exercise, radial-flow experiments are currently subject to detailed investigations. The advantage of radial-flow permeability measurement compared to linear-flow experiments are (a) the smaller number of experiments required for determining the in-plane permeability tensor of the preform and (b) a higher robustness of the experimental setup as race tracking effects can be generally excluded and sealing of the preform edges can be avoided. This results in a faster and more reliable experimental determination of the permeability tensor.

The present study investigates the influence of the experimental setup as well as the evaluation algorithm on radial-flow experiments by benchmarking test rigs developed at the Chair in Processing of Composites (LVV) at the Montanuniversität Leoben, Austria, and the Department of Polymer Materials and Plastics Engineering (PuK), Clausthal UT, Germany. The mechanical designs of these two test rigs differ significantly. Moreover, the image processing algorithms for detection of the fluid flow front, as well as the strategy for calculating the permeability values are different.

The experiments are conducted using natural fibre preforms within a range of fibre volume fraction from 27 % to 38 % and an injection pressure set point of 1 bar. In order to exclude any influence of manufacture, the preforms for both institutions are prepared by PuK. Furthermore, both institutions use a test fluid from the same batch and a common model for its temperature-viscosity-characteristics.

The study reveals significant differences between the permeability measured at the participating institutions. Cross-referencing the image processing algorithms and the strategy for calculating the permeability shows that they are source of discrepancy. However, the differences are small and do not account for the observed discrepancies in permeability. This means that, those discrepancies are caused by the differences in the experimental setup. Ruling out other factors, the authors conclude that different strategies for accounting for the pressure loss within the injection line are cause for the observed differences.

1 INTRODUCTION

Resin transfer moulding (RTM) and other LCM processes gain more and more importance in automotive, aeronautic and many other industries. In RTM a dry fibrous reinforcement is placed into a mould consisting of two rigid mould halves. The mould is closed and thereby compacts the preform to a specific cavity height. Subsequently a polymeric resin is injected into the cavity between the upper and lower mould half. Once the resin is cured, the finished component can be demoulded.

For high-volume production in automated processes, simulation of the injection process can be used for predicting mould filling time, required injection pressure and mould clamping forces as well as optimal placement of inlets and vents. These simulations are commonly based on Darcy's law [1,2], where the flow characteristics can mathematically be described according to:

$$v = - \left(\frac{k}{\mu \cdot \phi} \right) \cdot \nabla P \quad (1)$$

wherein v , μ , ∇P , ϕ and k are respectively the fluid's velocity, its dynamic viscosity, the pressure gradient across the preform and the preform's porosity and permeability.

Currently, the most reliable method for permeability characterisation is based on experimental methods. Two different types of experiments are known for in-plane permeability characterisation: linear and radial-flow experiments. For both type of experiments a three-stage procedure is followed: (1) acquisition of specific sensor data during the actual experiment, (2) evaluation of the sensor data to determine the advancement of the flow front over time and (3) calculation of the in-plane permeability from these characteristics.

Linear-flow experiments exhibit a one-dimensional fluid flow through the reinforcing fabric as shown in Figure 1 (left). In order to characterise the in-plane permeability tensor of the reinforcing material, three experiments are required. By contrast, the radial-flow experiment is based on injecting the test fluid through a central injection point causing an elliptical shape of the flow front when the fluid propagates through the reinforcing material (see Figure 1, right). Therefore, radial-flow experiments allow for measuring the in-plane permeability tensor with a single experiment.

Most commonly, optical measurement techniques are used for tracking the flow front advancement. However, other sensing approaches exist as well, such as linear capacitive sensors or an array of pressure sensors.

Figure 1: Example pictures from linear-flow (left) and radial-flow (right) permeability characterisation experiments conducted at PuK.

Addressing the ability to reproducibly determine permeability values, a round robin study has been published by Lundström et al. [3] comparing three different experimental characterisation techniques. In 2014, Vernet et al. [4] presented an international permeability benchmark exercise (to be seen as an extension of a first trial published by Arbter et al. [5]) following the idea of standardising linear-flow permeability measurements based on well-defined guidelines. The standard deviation values inherent to the results obtained by the participants were reported at around 25%.

Recently, Grössing et al. [6] benchmarked radial-flow permeability characterisation systems based on linear capacitive sensors. Two equal systems located at different laboratories were involved. Standard deviation values of the permeability values obtained for measurements on glass fiber woven fabrics were lower than 5 %.

2 MATERIALS

Fabric

The material used for this study is a flax fibre twill fabric. It has a nominal areal weight of 375 g/m^2 and a density of 1518.36 kg/m^3 . The material was chosen due to its excellent suitability for optical flow front tracking, good wetting behaviour in other experiments and due to its availability. However, as common for natural fibres, the fabric is not easily compactable. Therefore low fibre volume fractions in the range of 28–38 % were used in this study.

The fabric was cut and stacked by PuK to form preforms of five layers with dimensions of $360 \times 290 \text{ mm}$ (for LVV) and $290 \times 260 \text{ mm}$ (for PuK). After punching the central injection point into the fabric with a die of 12 mm diameter, the respective preforms were packed and sent to LVV. The goal of this procedure was to decrease the influence of deviation in the fabric and those of the handling and preparation processes. In order to determine the actual fibre volume fraction of the preform after compaction, each preform is weighed before the experiment.

Test fluid

Silicone oil (AK100 by Wacker) provided by a common source (PuK) was used for the experiments in both laboratories. Furthermore, the viscosity-temperature-characteristics of the test fluid were determined with a Couette rheometer system at LVV. The measurement data was fitted for the relevant temperature region with a two-term exponential fitting curve (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Viscosity-temperature-characteristics of the test fluid used for the permeability characterisation experiments (measurement data and two-term exponential curve fit).

TEST RIGS AND PROCEDURE

Test rig at PuK

The test rig at PuK (Figure 3, left) is mainly devised for optical tracking of the flow front in linear and radial-flow experiments. However it also allows for linear saturated-flow experiments. In order to prevent deflection, it features a stiff upper mould made from a 143–243 mm high, cross-beam-reinforced steel frame and an eight mm glass plate and a lower mould made from a steel block. The

cavity height is adjustable to any desired value between 1 mm and 10 mm by use of spacer plates made from thickness gauge strips. The mould is closed with two hydraulic pistons attached to a manual pump to build up a closing force of up to 100 kN. These features allow for an exact definition of the cavity height. In addition, the cavity height is measured after the experiment with the help of wax pellets, which are placed along the sides of the textile. The pellets are compacted to the cavity height by plastic deformation when the mould is closed.

For linear-flow experiments, the sides of the textile are sealed with a hardening fluid to prevent race tracking without causing distortion of the textile. Pressure and temperature data are recorded with sensors located closely to the textile edge at both, the inlet and the vent for linear-flow experiments, and at the inlet only for radial-flow experiments, respectively.

A proprietary pressure and temperature recording software and in-house Matlab script are used to conduct the experiment. The Matlab script provides a GUI to conduct the experiment. It sets the injection pressure (0.5–6 bar) and tracks the flow front by grabbing images from a camera with a resolution of 2560×1920 pixels and up to 3 fps. It also features an algorithm to detect the flow front on-line by using difference images.

Test rig at LVV

Figure 3 (right) shows a picture of the test rig used at LVV. The working table of the test rig is set up by standard aluminium profiles. Directly on top of the working table, the metal mould half is mounted. The security glass plate forming the upper mould half is made from two glass plates, each 19 mm in thickness, separated by a 0.76 mm thin polymer film. The glass mould half is framed with metal profiles in order to connect it to a hinge system on the backside of the test rig. A pneumatic cylinder finally provides for the flapping motion. The actual mould cavity is specified through cavity frames showing an inner dimension of 300×400 mm. The height of the cavity is determined by the height of the cavity frame. In order to provide variability for the cavity height, a set of frames with predefined and precisely measured thicknesses is available at LVV. This allows for modification of the cavity height with steps of 0.5 mm.

At a distance of about 1 m above the mould, a camera system consisting of an industrial monochrome camera and a precision lens with a focal length of 16 mm is mounted. The camera is used to acquire an image sequence during the radial-flow experiment at an acquisition rate of up to 50 fps at a resolution of 1392×1040 pixels. In order to determine the advancement of the fluid flow front over time, the sequence images are evaluated by means of a digital image-processing algorithm specifically developed for this application.

The pressure system consists of a pressurised air section, a pressure pot holding the test fluid and the fluid section. The pressurised air section includes a pressure control valve for providing the injection pressure set point. The pneumatic pressure in the pressure pot drives the fluid through the fluid section towards the injection gate at the lower mould half. Here, a fluid thermometer captures the fluid temperature during the experiment. The temperature value is used to determine the fluid viscosity by means of the viscosity-temperature-characteristics shown in Figure 2.

Figure 3: Permeability testing rigs in the laboratories of PuK (left) and LVV (right).

FLOW FRONT DETECTION AND PERMEABILITY CALCULATION

Although implemented independently, PuK and LVV follow similar strategies for determining the flow front advancement over time:

1. Creation of difference images for highlighting saturated image regions,
 - a. the algorithm at LVV makes use of the difference image with respect to the initial situation of the experiment, i.e. the unsaturated preform,
 - b. PuK calculates the difference image from images acquired directly subsequent to one another within an automatically defined region of interest
2. Extraction of data points along the fluid flow front
 - a. LVV uses image binarisation followed by morphological operations and image gradient evaluation,
 - b. the algorithm at PuK works with binarisation and makes use of a transformation from the Cartesian image coordinates to a polar coordinate system to find the out-most points of the flow ellipse,
3. Fitting of an elliptical geometry model to the set of data points
 - a. LVV uses a geometric model fitting algorithm with five degrees of freedom, i.e. major and minor ellipse axis length, orientation angle and centre point coordinates,
 - b. the algorithm at PuK forces the ellipse centre to coincide with the injection point centre of the mould setup, i.e. restricts the elliptic geometry model fitting procedure to three degrees of freedom.

In Figure 4 and Figure 5, the evaluation procedures followed at LVV and PuK are depicted for exemplarily chosen images.

Figure 4: Example image of a radial-flow experiment at LVV and evaluation steps of the digital image processing algorithm (left to right)

Figure 5: Example image of a radial-flow experiment at PuK and evaluation steps of the digital image processing algorithm (left to right)

In order to calculate the in-plane permeability from the flow front advancement and the obtained sensor data, LVV uses the iterative solution strategy proposed by Adams et al. [7]. At PuK however, an algorithm based on Chan and Hwang [8], which uses a transformation into an equivalent isotropic system, is incorporated.

5 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The permeability of the preforms was measured for a fibre volume fraction range of 27 % to 38 %. The results from the two participating institutions are shown in Figure 6. The results obtained at LVV (Figure 6, left) show data at four groups of fibre volume fraction between 27 % and 34 %. The steps

result from the variation of the cavity height with 0.5 mm step size. Within each group, five repeating measurements were conducted in order to increase the level of statistical significance. The statistical variation of the permeability values was calculated for the four data sets in terms of average and standard deviation values. The ratio of standard deviation value and average value was found between 2.0 % and 4.8 % for k_1 and between 2.6% and 5.3% for k_2 , respectively. Furthermore the average deviation from the exponential fit curve was calculated and found to be 7.5 % and 8.1 % for k_1 and k_2 , respectively.

Figure 6: Data and exponential fit curves for the experiments conducted at LVV (left) and PuK (right).

In Figure 6 (right) the results of the experiments at PuK are shown. The examined range of fibre volume fraction spans from 27 % to 38 %. Thanks to the possibility to use individual cavity heights for all measurements, it is possible to achieve an even spread of the 16 experiments across the examined range of fibre volume fractions. While this means that no standard deviation can be determined, it improves the reliability of the exponential fit. The average deviation from the exponential fit curve is 5.3 % for k_1 and 5.4 % for k_2 .

In order to allow for a proper comparison of these results, Figure 7 shows the data collected from the participating institutions together with their respective exponential fit curves. Furthermore two linear-flow experiments with fibre volume contents of about 28 % and about 38 %, which were conducted as additional reference, are displayed in the graph.

Figure 7: Comparison of permeability results obtained at the participating institutions.

As can be seen, there is a significant divergence between the results obtained at the two participating institutions. However, the radial-flow experiments at PuK and the two linear-flow experiments at PuK are in good agreement. Therefore a number of causes for the divergence were investigated:

Firstly a possible deformation of the mould was taken into consideration. However, the study was conducted using comparatively low fibre volume fractions for the purpose of ruling out tool deformation. Furthermore, the setup at LVV shows a lower structural stiffness than the mould at PuK. A resulting tool deformation, would lead to a higher apparent permeability with increasing fibre volume fraction, rather than to the observed reduction.

Secondly possible differences in the fluid viscosity, which are caused by inaccurate temperature data, were considered. Figure 2 shows that the viscosity does decrease noticeably with temperature. However, possible inaccuracies of 1–2 °C do not cause deviations large enough to explain the differences in permeability. Furthermore it has to be assumed that such inaccuracy would be systematic, hence causing a factorial shift of the permeability curve in logarithmic representation and not a change of slope.

Thirdly, the image processing algorithms were checked against one another by cross-wise evaluation of the acquired image sequences. This revealed a noticeable difference in the obtained permeability values, depending on the used algorithms for flow front detection and permeability calculation. Figure 8 displays the relative difference (in percent) caused by image processing and calculation algorithms for the experiments conducted at PuK. For this comparison, the image as well as pressure and temperature data from PuK were evaluated by LVV. The shown values are the relative differences between permeability values calculated using the image processing and evaluation algorithms at LVV and those calculated using the algorithms at PuK. It can be seen that with exception of the experiments at a fibre volume fraction of 27 % the algorithms at LVV lead to a lower calculated permeability. In average k_1 is 1.8 % and k_2 3.0 % lower, when the experiments at 27 % are excluded. While the resulting differences are not negligible and need further investigation, they do not account for the great discrepancies seen between permeability measurements from both institutions.

Figure 8: Relative differences in permeability values caused by image-processing and evaluation algorithms

The exclusion of the above mentioned possible reasons as well as the fact that the fitted permeability curves are in good agreement for a fibre volume fraction of approximately 38 % lead the authors to the conclusion that the divergence is caused by inaccuracies concerning the assumed fluid injection pressure. Whereas PuK is able to measure the true fluid injection pressure close to the injection gate,

LVV compensates the injection pressure set point with an analytical calculation of the pressure drop along the injection line.

With decreasing fibre volume fraction, the increase in transmissibility of the reinforcing material results in an increased fluid flow velocity. This in turn results in an increased pressure drop along the injection line. As shown in Figure 9 the pressure losses analytically calculated at LVV and those measured at PuK are in good agreement. However, the analytical approach solely considers losses due to wall friction at the tubing of the injection line. It neglects effects possibly occurring at instruments, which are located between pressure pot and injection gate. Both, PuK and LVV use tubing of the same diameter and approximately the same length. However, while a ball valve and a fluid thermometer are present in the injection line at LVV, that at PuK is only disturbed by the combined pressure and temperature sensor, which is located very closely to the injection gate. With increasing fluid flow velocity, turbulences at the instruments are assumed to become increasingly significant and thus to cause a reduction of the actual fluid injection pressure at the injection gate of the mould.

Figure 9: Experimental data and exponential fit curves of the pressure loss characteristics as measured with respect to the pressure set point (PuK) and analytically calculated (LVV), respectively.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this work, two test rigs for optical radial-flow permeability characterisation were compared with respect to the impact of the test rig design and configuration, as well as image processing and data evaluation procedures on the measured permeability values.

The results of the study show that test rig design and configuration have a significant influence on the measured permeability values. While the low fibre volume fractions were purposefully selected in order to rule out the impact of deformation of the optically transparent mould half, this decision caused an unwanted side effect: the high fluid flow velocity resulted in a significant pressure loss along the injection line.

These findings lead the authors to conclude that proper benchmarking of permeability test rigs requires taking into account the fidelity of cavity heights as well as the fluid flow characteristics along the injection line.

Furthermore the present work shows that the algorithms used for image processing and permeability calculation cause variations of the permeability values obtained. This asks for further investigations.

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